

MECHANISM OF PHOSPHORYLASE ACTION

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All the available data on the equilibria in phosphorylase systems have been correlated by a new theory. It is expected that this may lead to interesting results in the study of equilibria in other reversible enzymic processes also.

Equilibria in phosphorylase systems have been studied by Cori and Cori (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1940, 135, 746) and Cori, Cori and Green (*ibid.*, 1943, 151, 45) with animal phosphorylases and by Hanes (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1940, 129 B, 174) with plant enzymes. Hanes and Maskell (*Biochem. J.*, 1942, 36, 76) by an extensive study showed that when equilibria have been attained the ratio of the similar species of ions or uncharged forms of the inorganic and organic phosphates remains constant and is independent of p_n variation. On closer examination, however, (as we shall see later on) this hypothesis did not seem to work very satisfactorily and something remained still to be desired. In what follows, we therefore propose to develop a new interpretation of the nature of phosphorylase action.

A protein ampholyte undergoes in solution on electrolytic dissociation similar to the simple amino-acids, *e.g.*

For simplicity, we shall follow the classical method of writing these equations. The modern notion (Bjerrum, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1923, 104, 147) contending that the ampholyte exists not as HROH but mainly as $\text{R}^{\pm}$, leads to the same results but only from different lines of approach (Glasstone, "The Electro-chemistry of Solutions", 1930, p. 247).

Returning to the dissociation equations, as p_n increases, the basic dissociation is suppressed, while the acidic dissociation is facilitated. In the acidic regions near about the neutral ($p_n 7$) and for the proteins, which have their iso-electric points also in the neighbourhood of these regions, the prevalent forms would be HROH and ROH^- , the former predominating near the iso-electric zone.

The above ideas, of course, apply to the case of enzymes which are proteins.

The following assumption is then made:—

That the direct reaction, polysaccharide + inorganic phosphate $\rightarrow$ glucose-1-phosphate, is accelerated by the negative ions ROH^- , while the reverse by the uncharged particles $\text{R}^{\pm}$ (or HROH).

It may be noted here that the idea of only particular portions of the enzyme being catalytically active is not new (Goodwin and Hanger, *Proc. Soc. Exp. Biol. & Med.*, 1926, 23, 261; Northrop, *J. Gen. Physiol.*, 1925, 7, 603).

The exact mechanism of catalysis may or may not be through an enzyme—substrate complex (Michaelis and Menton, *Biochem. Z.*, 1913, 49, 333) but may also take place in a way similar to that suggested by Stearn (*J. Gen. Physiol.*, 1935, 18, 301) *e.g.*, through a preliminary activation process based on the approach of a dipole (or a charge) on a large molecule like an enzyme to the reacting molecules with a resulting change in the configuration and consequently in the energy of activation.

The whole process may be visualised in our case as follows : The starch or rather the polysaccharide molecules arrange themselves evenly round the enzyme molecules ; of the total number of polysaccharide molecules, however, only an active portion, with energy greater than the activation energy E , can react with the phosphate molecules and give rise to glucose-*l*-phosphate. Similarly only active fractions of glucose-*l*-phosphate can decompose. Hence if γ (starch)=(active starch) and γ_1 (glucose-*l*-phosphate)=(active glucose-*l*-phosphate) then according to the mass law

$$\gamma \text{ (starch). (phosphate)}^n / \gamma_1^n \text{ (glucose-}l\text{-phosphate)}^n = K$$

Since the full chemical equation is,

Let,

α = fraction of the total number of enzyme molecules that are in the form HROH.

β = fraction of the total number of molecules of the enzyme that are in the form ROH⁻.

C = (polysaccharide) in moles/litre.

F = (inorg. phosphate) ,, ,,

P = (organic phosphate) ,, ,,

[C may well refer to the " phase of the colloidal system in which the reaction occurs " and which " is maintained in a state of saturation in respect to a form of starch in true solution " (Hanes, *loc. cit.*)].

Now, the total concentration of polysaccharide molecules associated with the fraction of enzyme molecules that are in the state ROH⁻ is $\sim \beta C$; of this only a fraction, which has an energy greater than the activation energy E , will decompose ; hence the active concentration of the polysaccharide is $\beta C e^{-E/RT}$; so that $\gamma = \beta e^{-E/RT}$; similarly the active concentration of glucose-*l*-phosphate is $\alpha P e^{-E_1/RT}$ and the equilibrium constant K is given by

$$K = \frac{\beta C e^{-E/RT} \cdot F^n}{(\alpha e^{-E_1/RT} \cdot P)^n}$$

or at constant temperature,

$$\frac{\alpha}{\beta^{1/n}} \cdot K_0 = F/P \quad (K_0 \text{ including all terms which are const. at const. temp.})$$

Now, differentiating with respect to the $[H^+]$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d(F/P)}{d[H^+]} &= K_0 \left\{ \beta^{-1/n} \cdot \frac{d\alpha}{d[H^+]} - \frac{\alpha}{n} \frac{1}{\beta^{(n+1)/n}} \cdot \frac{d\beta}{d[H^+]} \right\} \\ &= K_0 \left\{ \frac{1}{\beta^{1/n}} \cdot \frac{d\alpha}{d[H^+]} - \frac{\alpha}{n\beta} \cdot \frac{d\beta}{d[H^+]} \right\} \quad \dots (1) \end{aligned}$$

(since n is very large $(n+1)/n=1$).

This expression can be integrated in the region of p_n close to the iso-electric zone; for near the iso-electric zone, the number of charged particles is at a minimum and α has a maximum value, or,

$$\frac{d\alpha}{d[H^+]} = 0$$

hence

$$\frac{d(F/P)}{d[H^+]} = -K_0 \cdot \frac{\alpha}{n\beta} \cdot \frac{d\beta}{d[H^+]} \quad \dots (2)$$

But

$$\frac{d\beta}{d[H^+]} \neq 0,$$

for β continues to increase (unlike α) with p_n . [It may be argued that the iso-electric p_n for proteins are rather sharp and our deductions will be valid only over a very limited range. But it is possible that as we move to higher p_n values, a net negative charge develops without change in the number of dipoles (*cf.* Cannan, *Cold Spring Harb. Symp. on Quant. Biol.*, 1938, 6, 7)]. In order to evaluate the expression (2), we consider the dissociation of the enzyme as a weak acid :

i.e. l g. ions of H^+ are produced from 1 mole of the protein, hence the charge on the anion part of the protein is also l units. l is an average value which remains approximately constant as the p_n changes in the regions we are concerned with.

[It has been shown by Cannan (*Cold Spring Harb. Symp. on Quant. Biol.*, 1938, 6, 2) that in the region of p_n from 5 to 9, the number of equivalents of H^+ dissociated from unit weight of iso-electric protein remains almost constant (*cf.* Cohn, *ibid.*, 1938, 6, 12)].

Hence, applying the mass law and if K_d is the dissociation constant

$$K_d = (\text{ROH})^{-} \cdot (\text{H}^+)^l / (\text{HROH})$$

Now, since β is small in the acidic regions due to the depressing action of the H^+ ions, (HROH) may be regarded as remaining constant and β would be $= (\text{ROH})^{-} / (\text{HROH})$.

Therefore, $K_d = \beta (\text{H}^+)^l$... (3)

From equation (3) by taking logarithmic differential

$$0 = \frac{1}{\beta} \cdot \frac{d\beta}{d[H^+]} + \frac{l}{[H^+]}$$

or,

$$\frac{1}{\beta} \cdot \frac{d\beta}{d[H^+]} = - \frac{l}{[H^+]} \quad \dots (4)$$

which being substituted in equation (2) gives

$$\frac{d(F/P)}{d[H^+]} = +K_0 \frac{\alpha}{n} \cdot \frac{l}{[H^+]} \quad \dots \quad (5)$$

which on integration, again, gives

$$\int d(F/P) = K_0 \frac{\alpha}{n} \cdot l \int \frac{1}{[H^+]} \cdot d[H^+]$$

$$F/P = K_0 \cdot \log [H^+] + A$$

(A is the integration constant and K_0 is a composite constant)

$$= -K_1 \cdot p_n + A \quad \dots \quad (6)$$

One point of interest is worth mentioning here; Kiessling's observation (*Biochem. Z.*, 1939, 302, 50) that two different enzymes may catalyse the direct and reverse reactions selectively (which has been proved untenable by subsequent workers) does not come in conflict with ours. According to the present hypothesis different ionic forms of the same enzyme act as catalysing agents selectively for the direct and reverse reactions.

Fig. 1.

Fig. 2.

From equation (6), it follows that K_1 will include l (the number of H^+ equivalents dissociated from the enzyme molecule) and also n (the number of glucose residues in the polysaccharide). Hence the equilibrium F/P value will be dependent both on the nature (presumably the source also) of the enzyme and the polysaccharide substrate. It is also clear that F/P will be independent of the total enzyme concentration, since this does not come up in the equation; and that if F/P is plotted against p_n , a straight line would be obtained with a slope $\theta = \tan^{-1}(-K_1)$, which would be characteristic for a particular enzyme with a definite substrate. The points of the graphs are taken from Hanes and Maskell (*loc. cit.*). In Fig. 1 (starch + inorg. phosphate $\rightleftharpoons$ glucose-*l*-phosphate with potato phosphorylase), it will be found that the points are all distributed evenly on either side of the straight line. In cases of brain and liver enzymes (Fig. 2 and 3) also satisfactory straight lines are obtained. The case of muscle phosphorylase is, however, of interest.

Curve A in Fig. 4 represents the reaction glycogen + inorganic phosphate $\rightarrow$ glucose-*l*-phosphate; Curve B in Fig. 4 shows the reverse reaction glucose-*l*-phosphate $\rightarrow$ glycogen (?) + inorg. phosphate. It would be noticed that (unlike the cases with other enzymes) the points on the straight line in Fig. 4, Curve A are almost always higher than the

Fig. 3.

Fig. 4.

corresponding points on the Fig. 4, Curve B representing the reverse reaction. This, however, is not to be expected if a state of true equilibrium obtains in this system, for then the same final state would have been reached from whichever side we approach it. Further, the fact that glucose-*l*-phosphate *in vitro* gives rise with muscle phosphorylase to a product which is identical with starch in iodine colouration, X-ray diffraction pattern and also in having an unbranched structure (Hassid, Cori and McCready, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1943, 148, 89), prejudices against any idea of true equilibrium being attained in a system containing glycogen, inorg. phosphate and muscle phosphorylase. Thus, it is quite probable that a simple equilibrium such as glycogen + inorg. phosphate $\rightleftharpoons$ glucose-*l*-phosphate with muscle phosphorylase does not exist.

We have already seen that hitherto the equilibrium in these phosphorylase systems has been assumed to be governed by the constancy of the ratio of the divalent ions $\text{HPO}_4^{2-}/\text{RPO}_4^{2-}$ etc. of the two acids, phosphoric and glucose-*l*-phosphoric. Hanes' scheme (cf. Parnas, *Ergebn. Enzymforsch.*, 1937, 6, 57) was as follows:—

The effect of the variation of p_n was supposed to be due to its influence on the dissociation of the two acids. Since glucose-*l*-phosphoric is the stronger acid, increase in p_n favoured its formation. Although this hypothesis works fairly well with potato enzyme, it fails practically completely in the case of animal enzymes, because

(a) the ratio of the divalent ions $\text{HPO}_4^{2-}/\text{RPO}_4^{2-}$ can hardly be said to be satisfactorily constant:

(b) the ratio of the monovalent ions show still greater divergence;

(c) Still more serious is the fact that this latter ratio shows statistically significant and systematic variation with p_n . Hanes and Maskell (*loc. cit.*) themselves doubted the validity of the above hypothesis in the case of animal enzymes at least;

(d) No cognizance has been taken of the specific enzyme effect. With different phosphorylases a slight variation in the equilibrium point is always found even with identical substrates.

Thus, there appears to be no other mechanism in the literature which can knit up the whole available data (both plant and animals) in a clean and systematic way.

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